

PRECISION FINGER PRESSING FORCE SENSING IN THE PIANIST-PIANO INTERACTION

M. Flückiger, T. Grosshauser, G. Tröster

ETH Zurich, Electronics Laboratory

mfluecki@ethz.ch, grotobia@ethz.ch, gerhartr@ethz.ch

ABSTRACT

Playing style, technique and touch quality are essential for musical expression in piano playing. From a mechanical point of view, this is mainly influenced by finger pressing force, finger position and finger contact area size. To measure these quantities, we introduce and evaluate a new sensor setup suited for the in-depth investigation of the pianist-piano interaction. A strain gauge based load cell is installed inside a piano key to measure finger pressing force via deflection. Several prototypes of the finger pressing force sensor have been tested and the final sensor measures from 0 N to 40 N with a resolution smaller than 8 mN and a sample rate of 1000 Hz. Besides an overview of relevant findings from psychophysics research, two pilot experiments with a single key piano action model are presented to explore the capability of the force sensor and to discuss possible applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The piano action connects the key and the hammer motion by a combination of mechanical levers. Due to the repetition mechanism the key loses its mechanical connection to the hammer shortly before key bottom contact. Per key, the piano action can be modeled essentially as a one degree of freedom system, e.g., as explained by Smith and Van Duyne [1]. This is the main reason why digital and hybrid piano instruments usually measure the key velocity parameter defined by the MIDI standard.

A pianist, while playing, relies on emotional state, kinesthetic memory, intended image, experience, motor control and feedback of the instrument to achieve a certain musical expression during a performance. There are different playing styles, techniques and interpretations of emotional expressions, that lead to a complex and unique interaction at the interface of the instrument: the keyboard and the pedals. At the keyboard the pianist's input mainly translates into finger pressing force, finger position and finger contact area size.

Regarding the interaction with the key, Goebel et al. [2] reported that pianists have a large inventory of different key press actions and techniques to achieve fine timbral

nuances. Further, it was mentioned by Tiedemann and Drescher [3] that expert pianists sometimes also use a unnecessary high pressure in quiet passages to achieve a certain musical expression. Independent of whether this quality of touch is audible in the generated sound, it appears to be of essential importance for the pianist.

We expect that this quality of the pianist-piano interaction is pronounced most in the finger pressing force. Therefore, this paper presents a new approach to measure finger pressing force with high precision for the in-depth investigation of the pianist-piano interaction.

The paper is structured as follows: Our sensor setup to measure the pianist-piano interaction is introduced, before the requirements for a finger pressing force sensor are discussed and the proposed design is explained and evaluated. Finally, the capability of the sensor is explored with two pilot experiments, where the piano key with the force sensor is installed in a single key piano action model.

1.1 State of the Art

Moog [4] was the first to present a keyboard capable of sensing finger position and after-touch force to augment musical expression possibilities of synthesizers.

Parlitz et al. [5] compared force measurements of amateur and professional piano players performing so-called tied finger exercises. For after-touch finger force sensing flexible printed circuit board (PCB) sensors with a resolution of 2 N at a sample rate of 80 Hz were installed on the key bed of a piano.

Grosshauser and Tröster [6] presented a solution to measure finger pressing force and finger position by using a flexible PCB with a force sensitive resistor based sensor matrix. Position and force resolution was 5 x 5 mm and 0.4 N, respectively. Data was sampled at 100 Hz. The participants of the study reported that the modification to the touch and feel of the key was perceivable but not distracting.

McPherson [7] followed another approach for the investigation of key touch features and presented a portable optical measurement system for continuous key motion sensing in piano playing. McPherson [8] also presented PCB-based touchpads that are installed on the piano key playing surfaces to capture finger position and finger touch area size by capacitive sensing with a sampling rate of 125 Hz and a resolution around 0.1 mm.

Kinoshita et al. [9] installed a strain gauge based force sensor on a fixed position of a single key mounted in an upright piano to study the relation of finger pressing force

and the generated sound pressure level. The sensor had a measurement range from 0 N to 100 N, a resolution of 20 mN and data was sampled at 900 Hz.

Tiedemann and Drescher [3] designed a strain gauge based folded aluminum beam piano key for finger pressing force sensing on the entire playing surface of the key. Several of such keys were installed in a grand piano for force and efficiency monitoring. The sensor concept seems promising, but unfortunately a technical evaluation of the sensor is missing.

Finally, we want to mention the contribution of Askenfelt and Jansson [10–12]. In addition to the in-depth analysis of the mechanics of the piano action, also cues about finger pressing force levels were reported, although they do not mention the setup that was used for finger pressing force sensing.

2. TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE SENSOR SETUP

Figure 1. Our sensor setup to measure the pianist-piano interaction. The sensors are integrated into the keyboard and connected to Cypress PSoC 5LP microcontrollers that convert and condition the sensor signals. The digital data is captured and processed by the host. Host and microcontrollers communicate by a serial interface. The PSoC platform can also be used to communicate directly with MIDI or OSC commands.

The envisioned system design to measure finger pressing force, finger position and finger contact area size by integrating sensors unobtrusively into the keys of a piano is shown in Fig. 1. The system consists of a keyboard with sensors that are connected to Cypress PSoC 5LP¹ microcontrollers. These convert the analog sensor signals into digital streams that are sent to a central host for capturing and processing. Alternatively, the PSoC 5LP platform also offers OSC and MIDI connectivity, which can be used in combination with the sensors to provide new musical expression possibilities through standard interfaces. The solution is scalable by design and can be used for several piano keys or even a complete keyboard.

In this paper, we only focus on the finger pressing force measured with a load cell integrated in a single piano key, therefore we concentrate on a subset of this system. The digital data is sent via the serial interface to a host computer to record and analyze the data.

¹ <http://www.cypress.com/products/32-bit-arm-cortex-m3-psoc-5lp>

2.1 Perception Thresholds & Sensor Specification

For the in-depth investigation of the pianist-piano interaction, disturbances to the touch and feel of the piano keys should be kept to a minimum and unobtrusiveness of the design must be evaluated. Further, the following findings from literature have to be reflected in a finger pressing force sensor design.

King et al. [13] investigated perceptual thresholds for single and multi-finger haptic interaction and found fingertip force detection levels around 30 mN. Multi-finger interaction has no considerable effect on these single finger thresholds. Pang et al. [14] studied force detection thresholds by letting subjects squeeze two plates, grasped by the thumb and the index finger. One plate was fixed and one was movable but resisted with a constant, controlled force. The just-noticeable difference they found was around 7%, independent of the reference value of the resistive force ranging from 2.5 N to 10 N. Askenfelt and Jansson [11,12] observed finger pressing peak force levels of 8 N, 15 N and up to 50 N for pianists playing staccato at piano, at mezzo-forte and at fortissimo level, respectively. Considerably lower levels were found for legato playing.

Engel et al. [15] showed that the timing of key presses by pianists varies in the same order of magnitude as the perception threshold for experienced listeners to detect asynchrony between two tone onsets, which is around 10 ms.

To sum up and by including a fair margin, an ideal piano key finger pressing force sensor should have a resolution around 10 mN from 0 N to 1 N and resolution relative to a few percent of the corresponding force level in the range from 1 N to 50 N. Data should be sampled at an interval of 1 ms.

2.2 Load Cell

Figure 2. Measured input-output characteristic of the load cell. RC refers to raw count. Resolution is smaller than 2 mN per raw count. Input force was applied with the compression test machine shown in Fig. 5.

There are different force and pressure sensors based on diverse principles available on the market. We decided to use

a Honeywell FSS1500NS² strain gauge based load cell, because of its miniature size, weight and satisfying performance in earlier projects [16, 17].

Fig. 2 shows the measured input-output characteristic of the load cell for a force input range from 0 N to 40 N. Using a 16 bit ADC, where one bit of precision is lost because of the differential load cell output, the resolution is smaller than 2 mN. The load cell outputs a constant offset, if no force is applied. This offset is set to zero in the measurements presented in this paper. The input force was applied with a test machine manufactured by Zwick³. The procedure is explained at the end of the next subsection.

2.3 Integration into the Piano Key

Figure 3. From left to right: small stainless steel plate, 3D printed support with installed load cell and piano key with the cut. Before the cut, the key weighted 78.6 g. After the cut the key had a weight of 71.3 g and all the other components together scaled 6.6 g. This sums up to a change in weight of less than 1 %.

Several sensor prototypes to measure finger pressing force in piano playing have been evaluated to optimize measurement range, sensitivity, linearity, deflection and force leakage, unobtrusiveness and mechanical stability.

The most promising concept is presented hereafter and is applicable to both, white and black piano keys. The sensor consists of four components: the wooden piano key with a cut, a 3D printed support to hold and position the load cell and a small steel plate. A picture of the components is shown in Fig. 3. The load cell is mounted on the support, before the support is aligned and glued on the first cut surface of the piano key. The steel plate serves as the counterpart of the load cell tip and is glued on the second cut surface. The steel plate and the load cell tip keep steady contact and the steel plate prevents the tip from notching the wood.

A sketch of the piano key sensor cross section is shown in Fig. 4. Due to the cut, the major part of the finger pressing

Figure 4. Piano key sensor cross section. Component arrangement, working principle and evaluated pressing positions P1 to P5. A: steel plate, B: load cell, C: 3D printed support, LL: lower leg, UL: upper leg.

force is deflected through the load cell, the minor part is leaked through the remaining wooden connection of the key. This leakage depends on cut position, cut length and cut height, and varies with finger pressing position along the endwise axis of the key. The cut height measures 5 mm and is given by the dimensions of the load cell, the steel plate and the 3D printed support. The length of the lever is the limit of the cut length, but the length also influences the mechanical stability of the key. The chosen cut has a length of 200 mm and was made at the center of the key height, due to symmetry and stability reasons. Prototypes with a cut closer to the key touching surface suffered from mechanical instability.

Figure 5. Finger pressing force sensor evaluation with the compression test machine. The steel peg has a diameter of 10 mm and a spherical tip. In this picture, the tip applies a controlled force to position P2 of the key.

The usage of up to three load cells in a row or with a triangulation approach was evaluated as well. However, the precise alignment of multiple load cells proved to be difficult, although using more load cells increases measurement range and decreases force leakage. Further, there is a limitation in the precision of the cut in wood working. To circumvent errors because of misalignment we decided to use a single load cell instead. The load cell position is a trade off between mechanical stability, measurement range and the amount of force leakage.

The sensor characteristic was evaluated by putting the key flat on a measurement table. The Zwick test machine was configured for controlled pressing with a steel peg, as

² <http://sensing.honeywell.com/products/force-sensors>

³ <http://www.zwick.com/en/products/static-materials-testing-machines/testing-machines-up-to-5-kn/zwicki-line-testing-machines.html>

shown in Fig. 5. The force was applied to five equally spaced positions on the piano key sensor. These pressing positions are highlighted in Fig. 4.

The result of this measurement is presented in Fig. 6. The finger pressing force sensor preserves the linear characteristic of the load cell, but shows a position dependency along the endwise axis of the key. For position P1, force input is amplified due to the lever connection to the load cell and this far most position from the remaining wooden connection has minimum force leakage. For the following positions, P2 to P5, the input force deflected by the load cell decreases, while the force leakage increases. In consequence, also the resolution of the sensor is position dependent. Position P5 has the lowest resolution around 8 mN but remains below the resolution requirement of 10 mN from Subsection 2.1.

Figure 6. Measured input-output characteristic of the finger pressing force sensor for input force applied to five different positions along the endwise axis of the key. RC refers to raw count. The corresponding pressing positions on the key are highlighted in Fig. 4. Input force was applied with the compression test machine shown in Fig. 5.

The position dependency of the presented finger pressing force sensor needs to be compensated for realistic pianist-piano interaction measurements. As finger pressing position is one of the important interaction parameters anyway, we are working towards a solution, which is not part of this publication.

However, a finger position sensor like the one presented by McPherson [8] would be suited to compensate such a position dependency along the endwise axis of the key. For compensation, a gain for each position of the data presented in Fig. 6 can be calculated and the actual gain for a measured position can be estimated by linear interpolation. A simulation with this approach and the presented data showed that a position resolution of 0.5 mm along the endwise axis of the key keeps the maximum relative force error below 1.5%. Sensitivity to errors is highest at position P5, because it requires the largest gain factor for compensation.

3. SINGLE KEY PIANO ACTION MODEL

Figure 7. The piano key with the force sensor installed in the single key upright piano action model. The action model has the same mechanics found in complete upright piano actions. The major difference is that the hammer hits a metal bar instead of a string. A: connection of the key to the hammer action, B: force sensor.

In the previous section we showed that the integration into the key preserves the characteristic of the load cell but the position dependency needs to be compensated with a finger position sensor.

To assess the dynamic performance of the force sensor inside the piano key, it was installed in a single key upright piano action model as shown in Fig. 7. This action model has the same mechanics as found in a complete upright piano with the major difference that a metal bar is hit by the hammer instead of a string. The compression test setup of Fig. 5 that was used for the static assessment could not be used for a precise dynamic evaluation, because of its limits in maximum velocity and sampling frequency⁴.

Hence, we decided to evaluate the force sensor in the piano action model by applying balance weights to the key, before the capability of the sensor is explored with two pilot experiments.

3.1 Evaluation of the Sensor in the Piano Action Model

The cut we made into the piano key generated two wooden legs of equal thickness: the upper leg (UL) and the lower leg (LL), see Fig. 4. The load cell senses in between these two wooden legs. Besides the desired sensitivity to finger pressing force, also modulations of the sensor gap height have an influence on the load cell output. Furthermore, the two legs have slightly different mechanical properties. The upper leg is covered with the white plastic touch surface of the key, which increases stiffness. The lower leg carries 6.6 g of additional weight from the load cell, support and cables.

⁴ Maximum velocity is limited to $0.025 \frac{m}{s}$ in contrast to typical key pressing velocities of $0.1 \frac{m}{s}$ to $0.6 \frac{m}{s}$ [11]. The applied force is sampled at 12.5 Hz. Position P5 has a key displacement range of ≈ 3 mm. This yields 1.5 force samples to investigate a key press.

Figure 8. Evaluation of the force sensor inside the piano key in the piano action model. The dots mark the measured force sensor output of nine balance weights that were applied at the midpoint of position P1 and P2 of the key. It takes ≈ 1 N to press down the key and launch the hammer.

This leads to a smaller offset of the sensor output in the case, where the piano key is mounted in the action model compared to the case, where it is lying flat on a table. Further, Fig. 8 shows the influence on the response of the force sensor installed inside the piano key of the action model, when different balance weights are applied to the piano key. Thus, the weight applied to the key and the load from the hammer action on the key lead to a small but measurable modification of the sensor gap height.

To give an indication of the order of magnitude, a change of the force input from 0 N to 1 N applied to position P2 of the piano key under test in Fig. 5, corresponds to a compression around $50 \mu\text{m}$ of the piano key and sensor.

The force signals presented in the following two pilot experiments are not compensated with regard to this effect and finger pressing position was fixed at the midpoint of position P1 and P2.

3.2 Dynamic Response to a Balance Weight

Fig. 9 shows the response of the sensor to a 100 g balance weight that was applied to depress the piano key installed in the action model. After the application of the weight, the key is accelerated towards the key bed. The dip in force level, occurring 16 ms before the maximum peak force level, marks the escapement of the hammer repetition mechanism. The maximum force peak is generated by the deceleration of the key colliding with the key bed, usually referred as key-bottom contact [18]. Meanwhile, the hammer strikes the metal bar and falls back for potential relaunch. This mechanic action is fed back to the key and manifests as a damped oscillation in the signal of the force sensor. In addition, a structure-borne vibration, created by the hit of the metal bar by the hammer, superimposes this mechanical action feedback. Thereafter the signal reaches a steady state value around 0.5 N, although 1 N was applied. This deviation was expected from the measurement presented in Fig. 8.

Figure 9. Sensor response to a 100 g balance weight that was applied to the piano key installed in the action model. A: escapement of the repetition mechanism, launching the hammer 16 ms before B: key-bottom contact, C: damped oscillation of the hammer after strike.

3.3 Measurement of a Finger Sequence

Figure 10. Overlay of five short notes played by a pianist at piano level. The notes were played with struck touch and the finger that presses the key was changed for every struck. The individual key strikes of the sensor signal were cut and realigned for comparison.

Fig. 10 shows the result of the second pilot experiment. A pianist played five short notes at piano dynamic level in a continuous recording. The notes were played with the right hand and struck touch. The finger pressing the key was changed from the thumb, to the index, to the middle finger, to the ring finger and finally to the little finger. For all fingers the envelope of the force signal shows the characteristic shape of a struck touch, cf. [9, 19]. Differences in peak level, in playing efficiency⁵ and in the shape of the force signal are apparent, although all notes were aimed to be played at the same dynamic level and with the same duration.

⁵ A possible definition of playing efficiency can be found in [3].

4. CONCLUSION

We presented a new sensor concept to measure finger pressing force in the pianist-piano interaction. The sensor is capable to sense subtle changes of touch in piano playing but demands a finger pressing position measurement for compensation.

Further, we showed that for high precision sensing inside piano keys, special care has to be taken to account for disturbances due to material properties. This holds in general for traditional classical musical instruments, where wood is often encountered as a material. In addition, also the disparity of different piano models and tolerances in manufacturing have to be considered, therefore slight adaptations of the presented solution will be necessary depending on the particular instrument.

In the dynamic assessment, we demonstrated that mechanical feedback from the piano action appears in the sensor signal. Finally, the finger sequence measurement serves as an example to show the sensitivity of the sensor to subtle variations in timing and finger pressing force.

We are convinced that the presented sensor is suited for the application in feedback analysis, efficiency and technique studies, as well as for the analysis of playing styles. Therefore, we plan to equip multiple keys of a piano with such sensors. Such a finger pressing force sensing piano keyboard will provide new musical expression possibilities, besides the access to the in-depth investigation of the pianist-piano interaction.

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